

Role of Civil Society Organizations in Social Adjustment of Orphans in Lahore

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Abstract

Children are the strength and future generation of the society and also maintain the culture and customs of the society. Due to many reasons some children who are orphan, very poor, neglected, sexually victimized children or rejected that have to live without their families and they grow up in Child Care Institution. It is a temporarily organized residential care for children where alternative care is provided who are in need of care and protection. Institutionalization refers to the process of implanting something within an organization, social system or society as a whole. This study was conducted to examine the social adjustment of the institutionalized children under the age group of 10 to 18 or above years. This study was confined to child care institutions run under the Punjab Social Welfare department in Lahore and 330 orphans (male and female) were selected through simple random sampling. This research study was quantitative in nature and data were collected using an interview schedule. After the field work data was analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). After the analysis the conclusion is that both orphans (male and female) have good social adjustment in child care institution. They feel comfortable in orphanages. The study shows that the orphans live happily in child care institution.

Keywords: Social Adjustment, Child Care Institution, Institutionalized Children, Affection, Love, Acceptance

1. Introduction

Social Adjustment is reshaping the social environment of the person. Adjustment means to adapt a new environment or changing from the environment. In this present study social adjustment means the total efforts of the children who face to adapt the new requirements of the society and also becoming the integral part of it. The other way to describe the social adjustment is a psychological process. It is an effort from the person to adapt the standards and desire values of the society that he can be adjust in the society. From these adjustments it's very important to maintain social harmony, peace and social adjustment and shaping the social safety network programs (Shair et al., 2023a).

The majorities of orphanages children come from very poor economic background families and also suffer from psychological problems due to socio-economic problems. The Index of Social and Economic Problems and the quality of school education were satisfactory in orphanages. The children were provided free textbooks and uniforms in orphanages. The social care home staff regularly monitored the appropriateness of education of children and there is a proper system for doing all activities (Mahmood, Ullah and Shah 2020).

The descriptive facts of social adjustment show low social balance between institutionalized orphans. At the end the result shows a huge distinction among both (male and female) orphans in case of adjustment. Many issues related to social adjustment found in child care institution among both boys and girls during the stay in child care institutions. They feel that mental health of children is not good in the institution (Talukdar and Barman 2019).

The lack of parents and parental care at early formative years leads to tragic results for an institutionalized children in the later part of his/her lifestyles. Despite the fact that the child is gave a trade alternative of being in a foster own family or in an institution a massive hole exists within the psychosocial need and psychosocial guide. Many research marked that this hole hints to mental troubles in the character infant in distinctive forms. Sometimes, children who lived in child care institutions face many problems in institutions (Priyanka, 2018).

The institutionalized youngsters had extensively decrease rankings within the expressive, receptive vocabulary, narrative abilities and psychosocial adjustment in evaluation to the kids raised in households. They examined that the psychosocial behavior of institutionalized children is much destructive than the others. The psychosocial and linguistic abilities of the children who lived in the child care institutions are examined in institutions (Asimina, Melpomen and Alexandra 2017).

Social Adjustment of Senior Secondary college students who lived in child care institutions. The findings monitor a fantastic full-size relationship between the intellectual health and Social Adjustment in the teenagers. He indicates that the adjustment level amongst senior orphans could be very high. They regulate him in establishments properly aside from who've underneath fifteen. The level of mentality of senior orphans is excellent. They take matters in proper way (Shokeen 2017).

The top-quality improvement of kids is taken into consideration important to society and so it's miles vital to apprehend the social, emotional, and academic adjustment of orphans. Children want a combination of intellectual

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competencies, motivational features, and socio-emotional talents to reach school. Emotional and social adjustment attributable to superb self-concept can offer the individual with some kind of potential to face the problems, and better self-esteem strengthens one's ability to efficaciously address with the psychological pressures (Alam 2016). The role of orphanages is making children more comfortable and polished about education, development and job creation. Staff of orphanages plays a key role in providing access to information and knowledge because a source of information raises awareness and brings them to the forefront of development. The contribution of orphanages to childbirth is commendable, started with the idea of helping children with one or both parents and being forced to use children and other dangerous resources for economic and social well-being (Hussain et al., 2023). According to the categories, all the necessary resources were provided to orphanage children (Abdullah *et al.*, 2015).

2. Methodology

Methodology is the process of carrying out a study. The universe, sample size, sampling technique, data collection approach and data collection tool and data analysis procedure are all described in this step of the research process. It also helps us to explain research design and techniques. One aspect of the research process is methodology (Crotty, 1998; Shair et al., 2023b).

This study aims to analyze the Role of Civil Society Organization in Social Adjustment of Orphans in Lahore. Consequently, Simple random sampling technique was used for the selection of respondents. At the first stage the child care institutions of Lahore district were selected for this study. At the second stage 15 orphanages were selected randomly. At the third stage sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane formula and 22 respondents were selected from each 15 child care institutions. Total 330 respondents were selected randomly from orphanages.

Data were collected through well-organized structured interview schedule consisted of close ended questions regarding the research objective. Univariate and bivariate statistical methods were applied for data analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Socio-Economic Attributes of the respondents (n=330)

SEX	F	%
Male	157	59.7
Female	133	40.3
AGE		
10-12	60	18.2
13-15	180	54.5
16-18	90	27.3
School Education		
Yes	330	100.0
Duration in Orphanage Center		
0-1 Years	42	12.7
2-3 Years	158	47.9
4-5 Years	104	31.5
6-Above	26	7.9
Comfortable in the Center		
Yes	328	99.4
No	2	0.6
Circumstances that brought in the center		
Death of Parents	255	77.3
Separation of Parents	68	20.6
Divorce of Parents	7	2.1

The data in the table no 1 is show that the sex composition of the respondents. According to the table the 59.7 percent were male respondents and 40.3 percent were female respondents.

The table shows that the age status of respondents who lived in child care institutions. In this section the respondent's age is classified into three categories. Respondents were the age of 10-12 years was 18.2 percent. Majority of the respondent 54.5 percent were the age group of 13-15 years and 27.3 percent respondents were the age group of 16-18 years.

The data in this table show that the education status of respondents. All the 100 percent respondents were goes to school for education. Child care institutions provide education facility to every orphan who lived in social care homes.

In this table show that the duration status of orphans in child cares homes. In this section respondents duration status divide into four categories but it is concluded that there is an minor section of respondents belonging to lower group 6-above years at 7.9 percent and the higher group 2-3 years was only 47.9 percent. Therefore, it can be said that the majority of respondents lived in child care homes from 2-3 years.

The data in this table show that the 99.4 percent respondents feel comfortable in the institution. So, we can say that the orphans feel comfortable during the stay in orphanages.

The data show that the circumstances that brought to the orphans in child care homes is classified in to three sections like, Death of Parents, Separation of parents and Divorce of Parents. The majority of the respondents 77.3 percent respondents come due to the death of parents.

The orphans are rise day by day in Pakistan. Natural diseases, natural disasters and conflict related deaths of parents and socio-economic issues of families are the main reason to increase the numbers of orphans. Research find out Pakistan is at number eight in the highest orphan population list. Lack of knowledge about the problems of orphan and lack of social policy in support to caregivers is the worse situation about caring of orphans (Kavak, 2014).

Table 2: Categories of the social services which provide to the orphans.

Services	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Counseling Services	1.2	1.2	5.8	37.9	53.9
Quality Food	1.8	0.6	7.9	50.0	39.7
Good Dress	1.2	1.5	6.4	41.5	49.4
Health Services	1.8	0.0	1.8	35.5	60.9
Education Services	1.2	0.0	2.1	48.2	48.5

The data of table no 2 show that the child care homes play a vital role in social adjustment of orphans. They provide all facilities to the orphan like food, shelter, clothing, educational, health and counseling related facilities. They provide protection and care to the orphans like national and international standards. In this table show that the 53.9 percent respondents were strongly agree about that the counseling services which provided to the orphans is good and lower was 1.2 percent about that.

The table shows that the 50.0 percent respondents were agreed about quality of food which provided to the orphans. Some of the 39.7 percent respondents were strongly agreed about quality of food. Mostly respondents were happy about quality of food which provided to the orphans is very good during the stay.

The data of table no 2 show that the majority of the respondents 49.4 percent respondents were strongly agree about that dress quality is good which provided to the orphans in child care institutions. Some of the 41.5 percent were agree about the quality of dress. Dee (2004) stated that the children homes opened to provide care and support to orphans but often times run into problems starting from a loss of budget to insufficient staffing.

This table shows that health services which provided to the orphans in child care homes are very good. Orphans were satisfied about the health services. Majority of the 60.9 percent respondents were strongly agree about the good health services were provided to the orphans and lower the 0.0 percent disagree about the health services.

A home where orphans get care, food, clothing, shelter, education, security and suitable environment to their physical, mental and social development in accordance with recognized medical standards. Orphans are under the supervision and leadership of trained members. Children are cared and accommodated in child care facilities temporarily until they can get family-based care (Ehsaas Report, 2019).

The data of table no 2 show that the services which provided to the orphans in child care home is satisfied. The data show that the 48.5 percent respondents were strongly agreed and 48.2 percent were agreed that the good educational facilities provided to the orphans in orphanages. The orphans were happy in the child care institutions because they get free education facilities from the management of the orphanages.

Social Adjustment is reshaping the social environment of the person. Adjustment means to adapt a new environment or changing from the environment. It is an effort from the person to adapt the standards and desire values of the society that he can be adjust in the society. From these adjustments it's very important to maintain social harmony, peace and social adjustment. Similarly the result of table 3 shows that due to social adjustment orphans make effort

to adopt the new environment. The data in the above table no 3 reveals that majority of the respondents 49.1 percent claimed disagree about they feel lonely in the institution. The orphans were happy in the institution. Most of the 49.1 percent respondents were also disagree from this statement.

Table 3: Social Adjustment effects on Orphan's

Effects	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Feel lonely in the institution	40.9	49.1	5.5	4.5
Feel nervous from the Environment	47.9	41.5	6.7	3.9
Feel uncomfortable In the institution	40.0	43.3	7.6	9.1
Feel under pressure To make decision	53.3	34.5	4.8	7.3
Feel worry about do not fit in the institution	43.9	39.7	9.7	6.7

The lack of parents and parental care at early formative years leads to tragic results for an institutionalized children in the later part of his/her lifestyles. Despite the fact that the child is gave a trade alternative of being in a foster own family or in an institution a massive hole exists within the psychosocial need and psychosocial guide. Many research marked that this hole hints to mental troubles in the character infant in distinctive forms (Priyanka, 2018).The data in the above table no 3 illustrate that most of the 47.9 percent respondents were strongly disagree about that they feel nervous from the institution environment while the 41.5 percent respondents were disagree. The data in the above table no 3 show that the 43.3 percent respondents were disagree about that they are uncomfortable in institution and most of the 40.0 percent respondents were disagree about this statement. Model children home give the free housing, training, books, hospital treatment and food to the children which lived in child care institution. The management of this institution fees a holistic development technique and focus on healthy development of thoughts, body and soul. To satisfy this goal children are given the chance to follow the extracurricular desires in sports activities, tune, dance and art. Children are also expert in local languages, technical studies, life skills, training and spiritual teachings (Bathina, 2013).

Table 4: Hypothesis 1

In staying here, I prefer to be provided with quality food * I am really nervous that I am not being good with the environment of institution.						
In staying here, I prefer to be provided with quality food.		I am really nervous that I am not being good with the environment of institution.				
		S.D	D	A	S.A	TOTAL
1	S.D	2(.6%)	2(.6%)	2(.6%)	0(.0%)	6(1.8)
2	D	2(.6%)	0(.0%)	0(.0%)	0(.0%)	2(.6%)
3	N	13(3.9%)	7(2.1%)	2(.6%)	4(1.2%)	26(7.9%)
4	A	83(25.2%)	73(22.1%)	4(1.2%)	5(1.5%)	165(50.0%)
5	S.A	58(17.6%)	55(16.7%)	14(4.2%)	4(1.2%)	131(39.7%)
Total		158(47.9%)	137(41.5%)	22(6.7%)	13(3.9%)	330(100.0)

Chi-Square: 28.318, Sig Level: .005, Gamma: .077, Sig Level: .392

The data in the above table no 3 show that the majority of the 53.3 percent respondent were strongly disagree about that they feel under pressure to make any decision in child care institutions while the 34.5 percent respondents were disagree.

The data in the above table no 3 illustrate that the most of the 43.9 percent respondents were strongly disagree about this that they feel worry in child care institutions and the 39.7 percent respondents were disagree. Children have feel over all support from the main persons around them specially parents and peers. These children appear with a high morale from those children who have below support from the others. To test this statement this study draw a sketch to explore the result of separation and lack of social or self-support from the children who lived in orphanages. Even

though basic services and shelter is provided in orphan care homes but the psychological needs are not met sufficiently in which result is stress and socio-emotional loss (Bee, 2000).

In this table chi-square value is 28.318 at the significance level of 0.005 shows a strong association between provided with good quality food and nervous that they are not being good with the institution environment. The gamma value .077 at significance level of .392 shows a strong association between provided with good quality food and nervous that they are not being with the institution environment. If we look at content of table there is strong excellent association between both variables. Instead of being providing good services like good quality food, shelter, dress and education the orphan's children also face many social adjustment problems like poor attachment, poor physical health, and mental health. The loss of parents is very difficult for the children's to live in the society. The effect of psychological problems remains long lasting on child's health (Cantor and Bajunirwe 2012).

Table 5: Hypothesis 2

I often get afraid in talking with others.*		I feel lonely in the institution.				
		S.D	D	A	S.A	Total
1	S.D	55(16.7%)	72(21.8%)	4(1.2%)	0(.0%)	131(39.7%)
2	D	62(18.8%)	82(24.8%)	2(.6%)	5(1.5%)	151(45.8%)
3	A	8(2.4%)	2(.6%)	2(.6%)	4(1.2%)	16(4.8%)
4	S.A	10(3.0%)	6(1.8%)	10(3.0%)	6(1.8%)	32(9.7%)
Total		135(40.9%)	162(49.1%)	18(5.5%)	15(4.5%)	330(100.0%)

Chi-Square: 95.204, Sig Level: .000, Gamma: .205, Sig Level: .021

In this table chi-square value is 95.204 at the significance level of 0.000 shows a strong association between often get afraid in talking with others and feel lonely in the institution. The gamma values .205 at significance level of .021 shows a strong relationship between getting afraid in talking with others and feel lonely in the institution. There is strong relationship between both variables. Care gave to orphans affects their upturn and improvement. Studies on institutionalization of orphan show that there is a full size impact of institutional care at the fitness of orphans. Institutional care has a negative impact on children fitness. They feel uncomfortable in institution. Care providers in the institutions the management have to adopt strengths and resilience based technique which focuses on protective elements and encourages the development of abilities and traits that assist in managing problems. This would work closer to improving the adjustment and problems of the institutionalized children (Padmaja 2014).

4. Discussion

Each country views that the children as an asset yet due to social, economic and parental conditions that they are often placed in dangerous situations. One such state of that situation can be an orphanage. A home where orphans get care, food, clothing, shelter, education, security and suitable environment to their physical, mental and social development in accordance with recognized medical standards. Majority of the orphans come to the child care institution due to the death of their parents. In child care institutions orphans are satisfied that the good services are provided to the orphans in orphanages. They feel pleasure to adjust itself in the institution. They lived happy life in child care institution. They want to do something in his life during stay in orphanages. They feel comfortable in childcare institutions.

5. Conclusion

Orphans are socially separated group. They have lost their self-respect and experience strong hurdles that prevent them from come to the front of activities that they get devotion. Orphan hood is a serious stage in the life of orphans who have strongly needed of parental and family care because it play an important role in the psychological construction of orphans behaviors as well as their social adjustment. Orphanages provide care to orphans who lived without parents. Orphans feel comfortable in child care homes. The child care homes provide good counseling services to the orphans. They provide good quality of food and health services to the orphans. Orphanages provide the quality of education for children who lived in orphanages. There is no main difference in the adjustment problems of rural and urban orphans in the social care homes. Children who have no experience of love and sympathy of parents tend to develop many problems.

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